

The First Temple in Jerusalem

also known as “Solomon's Temple”

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Entry tags: Temple, Levantine Religion, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Israelite Religion, Near East, Jerusalem, Religious Place, Judeans and Israelites

The temple is an important religious space in the context of Jerusalem. It has been destroyed, rebuilt, and appropriated by various people in its history. The First Temple, commonly referred to as Solomon's Temple, is the first iteration of this sacred space. While there is a physical site that we know would have encompassed the first temple, most of our evidence and descriptions are textual sources stemming from the biblical text. Original artifacts from the first temple structure are no longer available. Therefore, we are reliant on textual descriptions, references and traditions concerning the space. According to these traditions the Jebusites previously controlled the location until David conquered the area. He made this area the capital of Judah and ultimately a united Israel (2 Samuel 5). David was not allowed to build the temple because he was a man of war. However, his son could build a house for YHWH (2 Samuel 7). That son was King Solomon. The Solomonic age is credited with various building projects such as a wall around Jerusalem, and fortified cities around the cities of Hazor, Megiddo, and Gezer. However, the temple is one of the most important because of its religious importance. The importance is clear considering the specific details of the temple (1 Kings 5–6). Additionally, the author of Chronicles correlates the Temple with the sacred space of Mt. Moriah (2 Chronicles 3:1). Mt. Moriah was the location attributed to the story of Abraham and Isaac. This is the place where Abraham was asked to sacrifice his son, YHWH tested Abraham's obedience and also provided a sacrifice. This provision is the source of the epithet, YHWH will provide or YHWH Yireh. This project took seven years to complete (1 Kings 6:37–38). The house that King Solomon built for the LORD was sixty cubits long, twenty cubits wide, and thirty cubits high (1 Kings 6:2). Its structure was a tripartite plan. The first of the interior sections was the front often known as the portico. The second and largest area is the sanctuary or holy place. The last area was the inner sanctuary or the “Holy of Holies.” The sacred places of this tripartite plane were surrounded by various courts. This temple was most likely built during the 10th century and was destroyed in 586 B.C.E. by the Babylonians.

Date Range: 950 BCE - 586 BCE

Region: Jerusalem, Temple Mount

Region tags: Middle East, Israel, Judah

Jerusalem, Temple Mount

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Armstrong, Karen. *Jerusalem: One City, Three Faiths*. New York: Ballantine Books, 1997.
- Source 2: Trafton, Joseph. "Temple, Jerusalem." In *The Anchor Yale Bible Dictionary*, edited by David Noel Freedman, 6:350–68. New Haven: Yale University Press, 1992.
- Source 3: Shanks, Hershel, ed. *Ancient Israel: From Abraham to the Roman Destruction of the Temple*. Washington, DC: Biblical Archaeology Society, 2011.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.metmuseum.org/blogs/metkids/2020/solomons-temple-model-judaica>
- Source 1 Description: A reconstruction of Solomon's Temple

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Type of excavation:

- Pre-modern

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 150 years

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: The Pool of Siloam excavation project

Notes: There are many excavations but this one is currently being done.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Type of elevation

– Mountain

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Type of feature

– Mound

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Water feature

– Plantings

– Other [specify]: Walls and Stairs

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Multiple features

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ A group of structures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Sacrificial

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of war

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

In antiquity

– More than once

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

In modernity

– Renaissance

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: YHWH or Yahweh

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Groups:

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Specify

– Revealed by high god

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Earth

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Sand

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Clay

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Plaster

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Wood

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Humans

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Human narratives

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: A/N

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: A/N

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: A/_N

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: Wine offerings are part of some rituals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Bread, dough and various animals (meat) are offered

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Sacrifice of bulls, sheep, goats and doves

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Daily life objects:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: A/N

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: There could be as many as 1300 people serving in the temple complex at one time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Depending on ritual. There are daily rituals but there are certain rituals that coincide with special days such as Yom Kippur (The Day of Atonement).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Sacrifices are detailed in earlier literature such as Exodus, Leviticus and Deuteronomy. This includes bulls, sheep, goats and doves (with pigeons considered a suitable substitute). All animals must be ritually clean or kosher.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– obligatory for some

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Birth

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Death

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: A/N

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The eating that is associated is not a traditional feast. It is more of a reversion offering eaten by the priests. There is no formalized eating or drinking ceremony associated with the Temple

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: The eating that is associated is not a traditional feast. It is more of a reversion offering eaten by the priests. There is no formalized eating or drinking ceremony associated with the Temple

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: At least yearly in instances like Yom Kippur

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Unsure

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Divination through human communication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Divination through human communication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Divination through non-living material:

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Ark of the Covenant was used as a means to communicate to YHWH in various ways.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Present part time

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

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